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Brigadier-General Smith

Arrived with vengeance,
Barked his command:
“Kill everyone over ten.”
The town in woe,
Burned nipa huts.
Children drowned in sorrow,
Elder's eyes are brimming with tears.

The notorious general,
Marshaled his men:
More killing,
Burned the town.
Exultant and triumphed
Thousands died,
In howling wilderness.